

EFFECTS OF PROSELL ACTIVITIES ON LIVELIHOOD INCOME AND SAVINGS OF MAIZE FARMERS IN SOME SELECTED LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study assesses the effects of PROSELL (Produce and Sell) activities on livelihood income and savings of maize farmers in some selected Local Government Areas of Taraba State. Probability sampling was used to select 180 PROSELL maize farmers from 21 PROSELL communities. Frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and t-test were used to analyze the data for the study. The result of the study reveals farmers had a mean age of 45 years and 54.3% were male, the majority, (67.3% and 79.3%) were married, and acquired post-primary school education with a mean household size of seven people respectively. Majorities (78.7% and 76.8%) of the farmers were cultivating less than two hectares and had access to extension services with a minimum and maximum mean income of N179,122 and N672,000 before joining the PROSELL activities and minimum and maximum mean income of N427,122 and N1,200,000 after joining the PROSELL project. The result of t-test analysis reveals that, there was a significant difference in the mean savings of farmers before and after joining the PROSELL activities. In conclusion these activities educates the farmers on farming practices through the Farmers Training Business School (FTBS), improved savings through Village Savings and Loan Association (VSLA), access to fertilizer through, agricultural information from radio program and cash transfers. The study therefore, recommended that projects interventions that will better the livelihood should be given support by government. Also there is need for adoption of Farmers Training Business School model to better the incomes and savings of the rural populace.

Keywords: Prosell, Livelihood, Income, Savings, Maize, Farmers

INTRODUCTION

Produce and Sell (PROSELL) is a four-and-a-half-year (2018 – 2023) project funded by the European Union (EU) to improve the productivity and living standard of farmers in six Local Government Areas of Taraba State with a code name “EU support to food security and resilience in Taraba State” (Ox-farm.org., 2021). The local governments are; Ardo-Kola, Donga, Kurmi, Takum, Wukari and Zing. A similar EU-funded project is currently reaching out to 35, 000 households in Kebbi

and Adamawa State being implemented by Oxfam and DEC. (Oxfam.org. 2021). In the same vein, PROSELL is being implemented by Oxfam and Development Exchange Center (D.E.C). The overall objective of the project is to build the resilience of 40,000 small-scale farmers, fishermen and livestock owners (women, youth, and vulnerable households) in commodity value chains and rural enterprises. The project targeted 40,000 participants, 50% women, 30% youth and 20% other vulnerable household. The participants are heads of households or representatives of their

households. The PROSELL follows the success of Pro-resilience Action (PROACT).

According to Oxfarm.org. (2021) To achieve the overall objective of PROSELL project, Farmers Training Business School (FTBS), Fertilizer Distribution to Smallholders farming Households, Vegetables Gardening for women, Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA), Weekly Radio Program, Linkages (Farm Inputs and Organized Markets), Promotion of Tractor hiring services, Policy brokerage, Cash transfer (Conditional), Construction of grain banks (cash for work), Food Loan Transfers (small ruminants and Chickens), Tree seedling distribution and distribution of Fingerlings to interested fish farmers were designed to be implemented within the period of four and a half (4 ½) years in six selected Local Government Areas of Taraba State.

Income and savings are vital particularly in a developing economy like Nigeria, because of the direct bearing it has on the level of economic activities (Jaloet *al.*, 2015). The level of progress attained within the agricultural sector will largely depend on what the farmers do with the incomes generated from their farming activities. If such proceeds are saved, it will make capital available for further investment in the sector (Ekunyiet *al.*, 2020). In other words, the growth rate in the farming economy largely depend on the stock of capital built in a farm organization and the plugging back of such stock in form of savings for further improvement of the farm organization. However, if these increments are spent on household expenditure without building up the necessary investment infrastructure, the future economic development of the nation will be hampered. Adequate integration of savings and income generation programmes into development

strategies is capable of improving resource allocation, promoting equitable distribution of income and reducing credit delivery and recovery costs (Nwiboet *al.*, 2017). High-level income inequality exists in developing countries, therefore understanding inequality, and its consequences on agricultural production especially on how to improve the status of the chronic poverty-trapped individual farmers and farming communities through credit accumulation is a major concern (IniguezMontiel and Kurosaki, 2018).

Maize farming as a livelihood activity is associated with immense risks (climate change, pests, diseases, price fluctuations and changes in government policies). This phenomenon is more severe in Sub-Saharan African countries including Nigeria (Hassan, 2015). Farming households in Africa have increasingly sought means of escaping from the detrimental consequences of poverty by inclining to diversification of their activities; within and outside the farm sector. This is to primarily address their income and food security shortfalls (Osagieet *al.*, 2020). Livelihoods are typically understood in terms of the assets that a social group holds frequently, but not always; the activities or strategies that the social group employs, and the multiple outcomes its members seek to achieve—such as adequate food, adequate shelter, good health and nutrition, education for the future, and, critically, safety and security. Livelihoods must also be analyzed in terms of the policies or institutions that shape or impinge on access to natural resources, labor markets, education, social relations, and myriad other factors that shape livelihood opportunities (Maxwell *et al.*, 2017). In Taraba State of Nigeria, smallholder farming is the major livelihood activity of about 75%

of the population (Vosanka *et al.* 2019). They further pointed out the challenges facing the smallholder farmers are the use of local farm tools such as; hoe, cutlass, and axe, inadequate farm inputs such as; improved seeds, fertilizer, and agrochemicals and difficulties in accessing government-subsidized inputs. In light of the above, better livelihood is been threatened by low access to farm inputs, low linkages and market channels, poor access to agricultural information, and inadequate access to credit facilities implying low income and savings from farming since inputs are not sufficient. Despite so many attempts by government and NGOs to improve livelihood and build resilience of smallholder farmers in Taraba State through different types of projects, which has not yielded the required result. To bridge these gaps this reinforces the need to assess the effects of PROSELL activities on livelihood income and savings of maize farmers in Taraba State specifically the study describes the socioeconomic characteristics of PROSELL maize farmers in the study area; examine farmers output before (2017) and after (2022) joining the PROSELL project in Taraba state; compare livelihood income and savings of farmers before (2017) and after (2022) joining the project., evaluate the contributions of PROSELL activities to livelihood income and savings of maize farmers in the study area; and identify the challenges faced by farmers in participating in PROSELL project.

Hypothesis

H_0 : There is no significant difference between the paired sample means of the livelihood income and savings of maize farmers before and after joining PROSELL in project

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

The study was carried out in some selected local government areas of Taraba state to include Zing, Kurmi and Takum Local Government Areas. Zing Local Government Area lies between latitude 9°N and 11°7'N of the equator and longitude 8°10' and 11°50'E of the Greenwich meridian with the population of 2,294,800 (NPC, 2006), with a minimum temperature of 22.9°C and maximum temperature of 34°C. with an average land area of 1,030 km² (Adebayo and Oruonye, 2013) with a postal code 661. Takum [Local Government Area](#) lies at [7°16'00"N 9°59'00"E](#). Takum borders the [Republic of Cameroon](#) in the south, Ussa Local Government to the west, Donga Local government to the north. With a minimum temperature of 18.9°C and maximum temperature of 34°C. The area has an average size of 2,503km² with a population of 135,349 people (NPC, 2006). Kurmi Local Government Area lies roughly between Latitudes 5° 31' and 7° 18'N, longitudes 10°18' and 11° 37'E at an elevation of 872 265 m. It lies in an area of 1681 sqm with the population of 91,531 based on the 2006 census.

Source: Dept. of Geography TSU, 2021.

Method of Data Collection

Data for this study was obtained from primary source by administering of structured questionnaires to the respondents in the study area

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Multistage sampling technique was used to select samples for the study. In the first stage, it involves a purposive selection of 50% out of the six PROSELL participating Local Government Areas viz: Kurmi, Takum and

Zing local government Areas. In the second stage, 50% of the fourteen (14) participating PROSELL communities from each of the three selected local government to have seven communities from each of the Local Government to have a total of 21 communities. In the third stage, a simple random selection of sixty respondents were selected from the entire 21% PROSEL communities which represent 50% of participating communities, totally one hundred and eighty (180) respondents were randomly selected for the study.

Table 1: Sample selection plan for the study

Selected LGAs	Population	Communities	Sample
Zing	7000	Monkin A	8
		Yakoko	8
		Dinding I	9
		Bitako	8
		Mazang	9
		Bubbong	8
		Zing	10
Takum	7000	Manya	9
		Ruwa	9
		Kumbo	8
		Rufu	9
		Yukuben	8
		Kwari	9
		Bete	8
Kurmi	6500	Abong	8
		Akwengto Boko	8
		Ashuku	8
		Diddang	9
		Ndaforo Gwanda	9
		Njuande	8
		Nyido Toso	10
Total	20,500	21	180

Source: Pre-Field Survey, 2022

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage distribution were used to analyse the objectives of the study while inferential statistics in the form of t-test was used to test hypothesis for the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socio-economic Characteristics of

PROSELL Maize Farmers

The result in Table 4.1 shows that majority (59.1%) of the PROSELL farmers were between the age of 19 – 45 years with a mean ($X = 44.62$) and a standard deviation value of 19.94, This implies that most of the PROSELL maize farmers were young and active within the productive age can be able supply farm labor. This is similar to the findings of Ekunyi *et al.* (2020), Ndaghu *et al.* (2021), Adio and

Oladele, (2021) confirmed that most maize farmers were young and with active labor source for their farming activities in Nigeria. Majority (54.3%) of the PROSELL maize farmers were male. This implies that male dominated maize production, and they participated more than their female counterparts. Labour as requirement for farming activities, male physically supplies more energy to the field and thus, the reasons for the high participation. According to Richa and Shalini (2021), female participates more in land clearing and postharvest of crops while the male frequently engage in tilling, sowing, weeding, irrigation activities and pesticide/herbicides applications. Singh *et al.* (2023) also reported that female farmers participates more in dung spraying, transplanting and weeding while the male participates in land preparation, nursery, irrigation, buying of inputs, fertilizer and pesticide application as well hiring labor. Similarly Razzaq *et al.* (2023) reported that female participates more with post-harvest handling while male provides the on-farm labor. This finding agree with findings of Aladejebi (2018) and Oni *et al.* (2022) who all reported that male constituted the majority of maize farmers.

The result in table 1 further shows majority (67.3%) of the PROSELL maize farmers were married. This implies that married farmers constituted majority of PROSELL maize farmers. This result is similar to that of results of Oni *et al.* (2022), Adio and Olaoye (2022) and Emehute *et al.* (2022), who all reported that married farmers formed majority of maize farmers. Majority (79.3%) of the PROSELL maize farmers had acquired one form of education or the other. This implies that there is high level of literacy among the farmers. This is similar to the findings of Oladiran *et al.* (2020), Oni *et al.* (2022), Adio and Olaoye (2022) and Emehute *et al.* (2022) who reported

that farmers that had acquired formal education would likely be receptive to new innovations. Most 39.5% of the PROSELL maize farmers were from the household with 7 – 10 persons, with a mean household size of seven (7) persons and a standard deviation of 4.02. This is similar to the results of Agwu (2014), Ndaghuet *al.* (2015) and Idrisa (2016) who recorded a household size of less than nine persons among maize farming households. This finding is in conformity with that of Oladiran, *et al.*, (2020) and Oni *et al.* (2022) who reported the mean of household size was 5 persons. Majority (78.7%) of PROSELL maize farmers in the study areas cultivated less than three (<3) hectares with a mean farm size of less than two hectares and standard deviation of one respectively. This implies that PROSELL maize farmers are mostly small scale farmers. According to Bashir *et al.* (2018), small scale farmers are farmers cultivate 0.10 – 5.99 hectares. This study is in line with the findings of Olagunju (2016), Obisesan (2016) and Saminu (2018) who all reported in their studies that the majority of the farmers were small-scale farmers who often cultivate less than 2ha.

Moreover, a majority (56.7%) indicated that they have no other occupation apart from farming. This is in line with the findings of Reuben (2018), Kamara (2019), and Osagie *et al.* (2020) all found that the majority of the farmers had only farming as their occupation. The majority (84.8%) indicated had access to extension services. This shows that the majority of PROSELL maize farmers had access to extension services through the Farmers Training Business School (FTBS) which gives room for the farmers to meet with extension agents as such provides them with agricultural information to their representatives through the weekly representative meetings and further disseminated to other group members in absinthial by their representative.

Table 1: Distribution of PROSELL Maize Farmers based on Socio-economic Characteristics

Age	Response	Percentage	=	STD
19 -25	33	20.1	44.62	19.94
26 – 45	64	39		Min = 19
Gender		26.8		Max = 66
66 and above	23	14		
Male	89	54.3		
Female	75	45.7		
Marital status				
Single	43	29.3		
Married	99	67.3		
Divorced	5	3.4		
EDUCATION				
No formal education	34	20.7		
Primary education	49	30		
Secondary education	65	39.6		
Tertiary education	16	9.7		
Household size		5		
<2	7	4.3	7	4.02
3 – 6	43	26.2		Min = 2
7 – 10	65	39.5		Max = 11
11 and above	49	30		
Farm size (ha)				
<1	51	31.1	1.83	1.04
1 – 2	78	47.6		Min = 1
3 and above	35	21.3		Max = 3
Other occupation				
Yes	71	43.3		
No	93	56.7		
Access to extension services				
Yes	139	84.8		
No	25	15.3		

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Output of Maize Farmers before and after joining PROSELL Project

Annual harvest implies the time of year when crops are cut and collected from the fields, or the activity of cutting and collecting them, or the crops that are cultivated.

The result in Table 2 reveals the maize yearly output of the respondents before and after joining the PROSELL Project in Taraba State. On average, the maize farmers before joining the PROSELL project were producing 11 – 20 bags of 100 kg per year. Their maximum harvest was 42 bags and their lowest harvest was 2 bags. The variability of the mean stood at 6.75 bags indicating a big variance in the harvest among the respondents. The implication of the result is that low maize harvest coupled with a low market price may result in low income, which may affect the savings of the farmers.

After joining PROSELL, the average output of

maize producers in the research region was 26.70 bags of 100kg per year. Their greatest harvest was 75 bags while their smallest harvest was 5 bags. The standard deviation was 11.7 indicating a small variance in harvest among respondents. Farmers' output may have increased as a result of intervention by PROSELL that provided farm inputs such as fertilizer, agrochemicals, improved seeds, weekly radio programme, good agricultural practices through farmers' training business schools, and access to credit during village savings and loans associations meetings. This is similar to the findings of Mollah *et al.* (2021), who reported that NGOs assist farmers by providing agricultural supplies (seed, fertilizer, pesticide), agricultural tools, financial loans, agricultural training, irrigation facilities, and help for women in kitchen gardening, among other things, thus unarguably increase their harvest quantity.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents based on annual output(kg) before and after joining PROSELL Project in Taraba State

Before (2018)				After (2022)			
Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std.	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std.
11.20	2.00	42.0	6.7	26.70	5.00	5.00	11.70

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Income and Savings Before and After Joining PROSELL Project in Taraba State

Income is the amount of money realized from the sale of maize harvest. It is obtained by multiplying the total number of bags harvested by the average price per bag.

The result in Table 3 shows the estimated income of maize producers before and after joining the PROSELL project. On average, the income of the maize farmers before joining the PROSELL project was N179, 122.00; their

maximum income was N672, 000.00; and their lowest income was N32, 000.00. The variability of income among the respondents was 107, 920.5 indicating a large income difference among the respondents. After joining the PROSELL project, the average income of the farmers in the study area was N427,122.00. Their maximum income was N1, 200,000.00, while their minimum income was N80, 000.00. The standard deviation was N187, 215.50 indicating a small difference in

the income of the respondents. The farmer's income may have increased as a result of joining the PROSELL project which provides farm inputs such as fertilizer, agrochemicals, improved seeds, farm training business school, training on: Agricultural marketing fertilizer application, animal husbandry and records/farm management practices as well as the village savings and loans association which must have helps the farmers to save on weekly/monthly basis and had access to loans for farming activities. This is similar to the findings of Mara and Little (2019) who reported that an increase in farm yields resulting in higher incomes was recorded in households who benefited from NGO intervention schemes in rural areas. Also, Tauhidul and Emadul (2022) reported that farmer-beneficiaries of interventions had a lot of potential economic benefits derived from the schemes.

The result in Table 3 shows the estimated savings of maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL project. The average savings of the maize farmers in the study area before joining PROSELL project was N122,679.9, with minimum savings of N5,000 and maximum savings was N350,000 with a variability savings of N7,200.5 which reveals a

large disparity in the savings of the respondents before joining the PROSELL project. After joining the PROSELL project, the average savings of the farmers was N252,240.2, the minimum savings was N8000 and the maximum savings was N2,000,000.00 while the standard deviation was N225,422.5 indicating a large difference in the savings of the respondents after joining the PROSELL project. The increase in savings may be a result of the village Savings and Loan Association (VSLA) activity which enables the farmers to save on a weekly/monthly basis and the accumulated funds are disbursed to the members to enable them to carry out other activities and paid back after a maximum of three months period. This savings activity was seen as paramount among PROSELL farmers and as such it could be said to have been effective in proving the savings of participating farmers. This is according to Oxfam (2019), a figure to improve on and give more livelihoods to the populace. This is similar to the findings of Idrisa (2016), Kamara (2019) and Ekunyi *et al.* (2020) who reported in their studies that farmers had an increase in their incomes and savings after participating in projects aimed at improving their livelihoods of smallholder farmers.

Table 3: Statistics of income and savings (₦) of maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL project in Taraba state

Income	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard dev. (n = 164)
Before	179,122.00	32,000.00	672,000.00	107,920.500
After	427,122.00	80,000.00	1,200,000.00	187215.500
Savings				
Before	122,679.9	5000	350,000	7,200.5
After	252,140.2	8000	2,000,000	225,422.5

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Equality of Means

The analysis here considered the test of the null hypothesis which stated that the mean livelihood income of the maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL project is the same. In other words, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference between the mean livelihood income of maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL projects. The null hypothesis was rejected at a

99% probability level implying that there is a significant difference in the livelihood income of the farmers before and after joining the PROSELL project. The findings is in line with Karlana (2017) and Attanasio *et al.* (2019) reported a significant increase in the income and savings of smallholder farmers who received interventions and support from NGOs and spirited individuals than those who had not received any form of intervention.

Table 4: Result for the t-test between the difference in the mean livelihood income and savings (₦) of maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL projects in Taraba State.

Income	Mean	Mean diff.	t-value	Sign (2-tailed) n = 164
Before	179,121.95	248,000	14.697	0.000***
After	427,121.95			
Savings				
Before	122,679.879	129,460.37	7.006	0.000***
After	252,140.244			

Source: Authors computation from field survey data, 2022

Note: *** Denotes significance level at 1%.

The t-test result in Table 4.4 also shows the difference in the mean savings of the maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL project in Taraba State. The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the mean savings of the maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL project. Table 4.4 reveals that there is a significant difference in the mean savings of the maize farmers before and after joining the PROSELL project in Taraba state; thus the null hypothesis was rejected at 99.0% probability level. This result agrees with the findings of Ksoll (2016) who revealed in their findings that there was a significant increase in income and savings of

smallholder households who were assisted by Non-governmental organizations.

Contributions of PROSELL Activity on Farmer's Income and Savings

The Table showed the distribution of maize farmer based on HOW PROSELL activities improve maize farmers income. The result show that some farmers got educated through farmers Training Business School ($X = 1.62$) others improved their savings through the Village Savings and Loans Association with mean ($X=2$), others improve savings and income through increased fertilizer distribution to smallholder farming

improved savings and income through food loans distributed which prevented the farmer from purchasing food during off-seasons from their savings, while others improved their savings and income through grain banks which enabled them to store grains and sell out when prices were good. Knowledge of the concept of profitable maize production via the Farmers Training Business School (FTBS)

has seen more PROSELL maize farmers acquainted with strategies to improve their productivity coupled with the Village Savings and Loan Association has engaged farmers to save and obtain credit for the upcoming season. Without exception, the provision of inputs (fertilizer) to smallholder farmers has also affected the farming activities of PROSELL beneficiaries in the study area.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents based on the contributions of PROSELL activity on farmers' income and savings

PROSELL Activities	Yes	No	Mean (±)	STD
Educated on savings through Farmers Training Business School (FTBS)	132(1.60)	32(0.2)	1.62	0.989
Improved savings through the Village Savings and Loans Association (VSLA)	163(2)	1(0.0)	2	1.414
Improve savings and income through increased fertilizer distribution to smallholder farming household	137(1.7)	27(0.2)	1.9	1.062
Educated on savings through a radio program	31(0.4)	133(0.8)	1.2	0.282
Improve savings and income through linkages (input and organized markets)	111(1.4)	53(0.32)	1.72	0.760
Improve savings and income through cash transfer	67(0.8)	97(0.6)	1.4	0.141
Improve savings and income through grain banks to enable us store our grains and sell out when prices are good	25(0.30)	139(0.8)	1.1	0.491
Improve savings and income through food loan distribution which prevents us from buying food during off season from savings	93(1.13)	109(0.7)	1.83	0.071

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Challenges faced by Maize Farmers in PROSELL activity participation

The Table shows the distribution of challenges encountered by PROSELL maize farmers. The result shows that insecurity with mean ($X = 1.6$) and standard deviations of 1.142 were ranked as very severe constraints faced by PROSELL maize farmers, lack or no access to agricultural information with a mean ($X = 1.6$) and standard deviations of 0.435 was a less severe constraint, while climate changes, inaccessible road networks, inadequate marketing channels and depleted soil/soil texture with mean ($X = 2.52, 2.41, 2.4, 2.0$) and standard deviations of 0.750, 0.748, 0.386 and 0.343 were seen as severe constraints faced by PROSELL maize farmers, on the other hand, inadequate access to inputs ($X = 0.7$) and land tenure system with mean ($X = 1.9$) and a standard deviation value of 0.240 was seen as less severe constraints faced by PROSELL maize farmers in pursuing livelihoods derived from maize farming. This shows that farmers were unable to put part of what they earn aside for use in the future, as such inability to save is an inadequacy of income which was identified. This is in line with the findings of Osondu¹, Obike, and Ogbonna (2022) who found out that maize farmers' incomes are notable to meet their needs let alone some being left for savings. While Ethan (2019) found out that though farmers always try and wish to save, they are unable to do so due to their limited incomes.

Table 8: Distribution of challenges faced by PROSELL Maize Farmers

Challenges of PROSELL maize farmers	Very Severe	Severe	Not Severe	Mean	STD
Climate changes	86(1.6)	67(0.82)	11(0.1)	2.52	0.750
Inaccessible road networks	88(1.61)	55(0.67)	21(0.13)	2.41	0.748
Inadequate access to input	124(2.27)	361(0.44)	4(0.0)	2.71	1.204
Poor access to agricultural information	16(0.3)	14(0.2)	164(1)	1.6	0.435
Inadequate marketing channels	61(1.12)	55(0.67)	48(0.6)	2.4	0.282
No access to credit/loan	19(0.3)	21(0.3)	94(0.1)	0.7	1.142
Insecurity	121(2.21)	43(0.52)	0(0)	2.73	1.16
Soil texture	57(1.04)	45(0.55)	62(0.38)	2.0	0.343
Land tenure system	48(0.88)	51(0.62)	65(0.4)	1.9	0.240

Source: Field Survey, 2022

(Figures in parenthesis are mean scores)

Conclusion

It could be concluded that the PROSELL project had improved the income and savings of maize farmers who were beneficiaries of the project through the provision of inputs such as fertilizer, seeds, and agrochemicals with the farmer's training business school and village

savings and loan association which helped promote their savings habits. Based on the results of the findings, Oxfam through PROSELL should provide other farm inputs such as so as improved seeds, herbicides, insecticides and other farm inputs for increased productivity.

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